

ANÁLISIS DEL ENFOQUE CENTRADO EN EL ALUMNO EN LA ELABORACIÓN DE BREVES INFORMES ESCRITOS CON ALUMNOS DE PRIMER NIVEL DEL CENID DE LA UNIVERSIDAD TÉCNICA DE BABAHOYO

ANALYSIS OF THE STUDENT-CENTERED APPROACH IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF BRIEF WRITTEN REPORTS WITH FIRST LEVEL STUDENTS AT CENID AT TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF BABAHOYO

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RESUMEN

Este trabajo de investigación se desarrolló con el fin de incentivar los procesos cognitivos de

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la escritura en inglés a través de diferentes composiciones en los alumnos de Primer Nivel del CENID. Para la recolección de información se ha utilizado una metodología basada en la elaboración de una encuesta a estudiantes y una entrevista a docentes enfocada en las dos variables. A través de la encuesta y entrevista se encontró una relación directa con la producción de trabajos escritos en idioma inglés, lo que constató que los estudiantes no desarrollan adecuadamente las habilidades escritas, presentando fallas en la organización y producción de sus escritos. Adicionalmente, se encontró que los docentes no utilizan herramientas didácticas durante el proceso de enseñanza y aprendizaje, razón por la cual los estudiantes no mejoran la escritura del idioma inglés. Por tanto, si se aplica esta herramienta, será más fácil para los estudiantes desarrollar mejor el proceso de escritura y por ende su rendimiento académico.

***Palabras clave:** Reportes escritos, formación integral, integración, desarrollo de aptitudes.*

ABSTRACT

This research work was developed in order to encourage the cognitive processes of writing in English through different compositions in the First Level students at CENID. For the collection of information, a methodology based on the elaboration of a survey of students and an interview with teachers focused on the two variables has been used. Through the survey and interview, a direct relationship to the production of written works in the English language was found, which verified that students do not develop written skills properly, presenting faults in the organization and production of their writings. Additionally, it was found that teachers do not use didactic tools during the process of teaching and learning, which is why students do not improve the writing of the English language. Therefore, if this tool is applied, it will make it easier for students to better develop the writing process and thus their academic performance.

Keywords: Written reports, integral formation, education, develop aptitudes.

INTRODUCTION

In order to achieve the multifaceted and integral formation of man, it is necessary to know at least one foreign language. English as an international language that makes it possible to consult what is being researched and published in other parts of the world in the different branches of knowledge, as well as to publish his research in this language (Heitmann & Hecht, 2017).

The study of English is part of all university degrees, so its learning requires great importance. One of its objectives is precise that the future professional is able to read and consult specialized bibliography in English language independently to expand their knowledge (Olmo, 2016). In fact, the student needs to be intrinsically motivated, this motivation is achieved throughout his career with the use of different methods, techniques, and active procedures in the process of teaching language learning (Anjomshoa, 2015)

The university graduate must be par excellence a transformer of society and his natural environment must have full control of the contents of his science, in order to express his ideas and act effectively and efficiently in solving the problems of his future as a professional. The student will face real problems in his future job, so one of the ways in which the student will be able to access the necessary information and the use of technology is precisely the command of the English language, both orally and in writing. Writing is the most complex ability compared to others. When writing, one must have indirect communication ability, language structure, writing techniques, and the ability to extract ideas form text. (Aceng Hasani, 2016)

In spite of the fact that the national education system includes the teaching of foreign languages to achieve the integral formation of the new generations (Harrison, 2017), even from the fifth grade in some schools (primary education) the students upon entering the university still present difficulties in the adequate use of the different morph syntactic and lexical structures that are present both in the communicative functions that are studied and in the ability to write, which makes oral or written communication in the foreign language impossible (Tremblay & Lalancette, 2012).

Certainly, written language is much more demanding than oral. Although the language

resources are the same, the grammar and semantics used in the former are more complex and varied. Furthermore, because the receiver and the sender are not in the physical presence of each other, the sender has to make a great effort to analyze which contextual elements are essential in order to be understood and to make his perceptions sufficiently explicit using only the written language.

It coincides with the important linguist Silberstein (2017) in his criterion about the complexity and exigency of the written production. In this regard he states that writing a mother tongue is one of the most complicated tasks and becomes a challenge for students, as few are those who master it; learning to do it well is a slow and difficult process, it also causes anxiety and frustration in many students. Silberstein (2017) adds that to teach writing it is not simple to represent language through visible elements, as Burns (2019) states, the objective of this is to transmit correct information in an effective and appropriate way.

In addition, the ability to write English is a limiting factor in the production of texts due to the lack of training for teachers and directors in the use of new techniques that encourage the development of creativity and allow the written language to flow in CENID of the Technical University of Babahoyo. After analyzing the problem in its context and having studied alternative solutions, the need arises to plan solutions as a proposal to improve the development of writing skills through a student-centered approach.

In Ecuador the teaching of the English Language is emphasized more in the oral skill than the written one (Cambridge University Press, 2018), for this reason the great difficulty is presented in the writing of texts in Spanish, Similar to Muhsin (2016), who expresses that a similar situation occurs in English because there is not a developed skill in the writing. The educational evolution in our environment has evidenced a limited production of texts, books, magazines, and essays that are published within the Spanish language has as main consequence the scarce dexterity to write, reason why the difficulties in the development of the dexterity of writing are due to the lack of knowledge of strategies and innovative techniques on the part of the teacher in his performance, causing in the student a deficient process of learning of the language.

In the Province of Los Ríos, the level of English is considered to be within a low rank according to the Ministry of Education (2015). According to old examinations made to

students of educational institutions, only cities like Quito, Guayaquil, Cuenca and Loja stand out according to the percentage of correct writing of the English language, positioning to Ecuador in the position number 81 of the ranking of world-wide dominion of the English language (EF English Proficiency Index, 2019). This value is given due to the fact that the learning of this language continues to be carried out through traditional and monotonous classes, causing the student to be disinterested in producing his or her own ideas, in addition to the scarce training that exists in the teachers who teach the subject (Hilleni, 2016).

This situation has deepened due to the fact that in the learning of the English language mechanized and little dynamic techniques are used, that is limited only to the repetition and not to develop the creativity to structure paragraphs and texts, sentences, essays in the English language (Khan Academy, 2018).

The CENID belonging to the Technical University of Babahoyo, where the research will be carried out, does not escape from this reality; all of the above converges in limited capacity of students to elaborate simple phrases and sentences about a specific topic, where they live and what they do. Although students can understand ready-made phrases, basic structures and simple sentence forms, they are not yet able to use the language in any practical work situation or more technical, such as essay writing. In order to reduce the lack of knowledge of adequate techniques and strategies in the development of writing skills.

For this reason, it is fundamental to implement in the teaching exercise active, creative and motivating techniques that facilitate the learning of this language, generating students stimulated to learn and at the same time to develop this skill.

If there is no solution to the problem of English Language Learning in CENID, there will continue to be an inoperative and unfruitful practice of learning the English language, and therefore it would be impossible to develop the sub-skills of writing. In this research, the use of standard grammar to express a particular meaning will be focused which are the correct use of pronouns, writing topic sentences, developing ideas, writing fluency and generating correctly structured quality sentences.

On the other hand, there would be from students' scarce knowledge of the English language, insufficient written practice, difficulty in developing this skill; students will be formed as receptive, repetitive, passive beings who will not be able to develop aptitudes, significant

learning in the area, and therefore will not be able to reach adequate levels of communicative competence to express themselves in the English language. This situation will not only harm their academic performance but also their future professional life since today the command of the English language is the basis for access to other fields. The interest of the present investigation is justified in the learning that the students have obtained during the classes given by the teachers, the student has reached only partially the knowledge of vocabulary, grammatical rules, to develop in an effective way the ability to write in English simple phrases and sentences about a specific topic in order to contrast them and create a writing that has grammatical structure correct and understandable for both the student and the teacher.

It is important to build a better educational future, starting by not being traditional but having innovative classes, practices where students are facilitated to use their own imagination and create their own history, this will allow us to improve inter learning and know the extent to which the theoretical-practical knowledge of the English language will facilitate students the mastery of the skill of "writing" during the sessions taught by teachers in the area, and in turn highlight the aspects that must be considered to strengthen this skill.

The beneficiaries of this investigation will be the students, since through these techniques they will be able to acquire better learning to develop this skill of writing in English, in stories, texts, essays in a correct and fluent way.

Research Questions:

- What are the main challenges First Level students at CENID at Technical University of Babahoyo encounter when writing reports?
- How do strategies based on student-centered approach can benefit the development of writing reports?
- How does the implementation of student-centered activities assist the learners in their efforts to develop writing reports?
- To investigate the effect that First Level students at CENID at Technical University of Babahoyo face when acquiring writing communication skills by means of a survey

applied with First Level students to propose variety strategies and activities based on student-centered approach.

General objective

- To encourage the cognitive processes of writing in English through different compositions in the first level First Level students at CENID.

Specific Objectives:

- To identify the challenges of First Level students at CENID at Technical University of Babahoyo in developing written reports.
- To analyze the benefits and limitations of both teacher-centered and learner-centered approaches in the teaching of written reports.
- To plan a proposal for enhancing the development of writing communication-based on the Action-Oriented Approach.

METHODOLOGY

The chapter describes the research methodology that has been applied to solve the problem at Language Center – CENID. The approach taken was action research as it aims to find or propose a solution for a problem.

This approach is valid to the study, because it consists as a process of inquiry will be followed to obtain the results. In addition, six steps have to be followed. The process goes as follows:

1. Identify a problem to be studied
2. Collect data on the problem
3. Organize, analyze, and interpret the data
4. Develop a plan to address the problem
5. Implement the list of activities
6. Evaluate the results of the actions taken

3.1. Participants

The participants selected for the study were first level students at CENID at technical university of Babahoyo. In the same way, five educators of the subject of English were selected.

The students were between the ages of 16 and 19. The data collection process was done during class hours in the respective subject area of English. For the collection of data, it was necessary the authorization of the director and pass of the academic board, documents that have been properly annexed in this work of investigation. The research is feasible because there is full access to work with the participants of this study. In addition, each activity was carried out with the corresponding students assigned to the author. The collaboration of the author's colleagues was essential to the development of this document.

3.2. Data Collection Techniques and Instruments

The instruments and techniques were chosen in relation to objectives created after the analysis of the problem statement. Such instruments and techniques are the following:

Table 1 Data collection

Number	Variable	Detail
1	For what?	To achieve the objective of the research
2	To whom?	first level students at CENID at technical university of Babahoyo
3	On what aspects?	Oral communication
4	Who?	Researcher
5	When?	2018
6	Which techniques will be used by the researcher?	Survey

Elaborated by: Beltrán Miguel, Cifuentes Thalia, García Paola and Menéndez Carlos, 2019

The research technique used was a survey, a document that presents a series of properly structured questions aimed at students. In the survey, students were asked to give their perception of their current situation according to the approach the teacher provides when

teaching writing skills (See Appendix 1).

Similarly, an interview was conducted with the teachers, in which they answered questions about their methodology for teaching English, focusing on writing skills (see Appendix 2).

It should be noted that each of the data collection instruments has been validated by their respective authors, as all the elements considered have been adapted from several of the authors who have carried out preliminary and similar studies.

4. Data analysis

Survey of students of first level students at CENID at technical university of Babahoyo

1. Does the English teacher apply classroom projects, which allow to practice the written skills of the language?

Table 2 The teacher applies classroom projects

Alternatives	Frequency	Percentage
Always	2	5%
Frequently	12	30%
Sometimes	24	60%
Rarely	1	3%
Never	1	3%
Total	40	100%

Elaborated by: Beltrán Miguel, Cifuentes Thalia, García Paola and Menéndez Carlos, 2019

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According to the results expressed by the students, sometimes the teacher carries out activities such as projects that allow the practice of writing skills, representing 60%, and 30% mention that these activities are frequently carried out. However, only 5% consider that these classroom strategies are used in a mandatory way in the classroom.

2. Are there individual or group works in the English classes that allow to reinforce new information about the revised topics?

Table 3 Allow to reinforce new information

Alternatives	Frequency	Percentage
Always	3	8%
Frequently	4	10%
Sometimes	30	75%
Rarely	3	8%
Never	0	0%
Total	40	100%

Elaborated by: Beltrán Miguel, Cifuentes Thalia, García Paola and Menéndez Carlos, 2019

Elaborated by: Beltrán Miguel, Cifuentes Thalia, García Paola and Menéndez Carlos, 2019

According to the results obtained from the survey, there are individual and group activities that encourage writing in students, which allow them to collect information according to the topic being studied. However, the frequency with which it is applied is minimal. For 75% of students say that only sometimes such activities are developed. This is a value that should be taken into consideration, since for the development of adequate writing in students, one should start with basic concepts and appropriate tasks that promote this knowledge.

3. How often do you do essays or learning journals as an activity during English inter-language learning?

Table 4 Essays or learning journals as an activity

Alternatives	Frequency	Percentage
Always	2	5%
Frequently	2	5%
Sometimes	3	8%
Rarely	32	80%
Never	1	3%
Total	40	100%

Elaborated by: Beltrán Miguel, Cifuentes Thalia, García Paola and Menéndez Carlos, 2019

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Essays and learning journals are inappropriate for students in study, as their level does not apply to such activities. However, it is necessary to begin by structuring grammatical sentences with meaning, in order to begin to develop small paragraphs throughout their study. Therefore, the value that determines the survey agrees with the perspective of the professors of the bibliography, being rarely (80%) that activities are carried out that include academic essays and derivatives.

4. Does the teacher apply tables of what is known, what is wanted and what is going to be learned about a topic during the English class?

Table 5 The teacher applies tables

Alternatives	Frequency	Percentage
Always	0	0%
Frequently	0	0%
Sometimes	1	3%
Rarely	38	95%
Never	1	3%
Total	40	100%

Elaborated by: Beltrán Miguel, Cifuentes Thalia, García Paola and Menéndez Carlos, 2019

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According to the results determined in the survey about the development of tables that indicate what is known, what is desired to know and what will be learned, 95% mention that it is very rare for this type of activities to be carried out. This indicates that students are not aware of what they are learning and how they can use it for their future. According to the values observed, it is considered necessary to apply this strategy so that the students can better adopt their vision of writing in the English language.

5. Do the activities presented during the inter-learning process teach real or fictitious problems?

Table 6 The teacher uses real or fictitious problems

Alternatives	Frequency	Percentage
Always	1	3%
Frequently	15	38%
Sometimes	20	50%
Rarely	2	5%
Never	2	5%
Total	40	100%

Elaborated by: Beltrán Miguel, Cifuentes Thalia, García Paola and Menéndez Carlos, 2019

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The activities that are carried out by the teacher are usually fictitious situations and in some cases are real. According to the results expressed by the students, 50% indicate that these types of activities are sometimes carried out, where fiction and reality are contrasted to generate ideas and can be applied to writing skills. On the other hand, 38% of students state that this type of task is frequently carried out by the teacher, which contributes greatly to the development and understanding of the students.

6. Do the writing activities presented in English class allow students to express ideas, emotions, or opinions?

Table 7 Allow students to express ideas, emotions, or opinions

Alternatives	Frequency	Percentage
Always	2	5%
Frequently	20	50%
Sometimes	11	28%
Rarely	4	10%
Never	3	8%
Total	40	100%

Elaborated by: Cifuentes Thalia, 2019

Elaborated by: Beltrán Miguel, Cifuentes Thalia, García Paola and Menéndez Carlos, 2019

According to the results expressed by the students, half of the class representing 50% mentions that frequently these activities are carried out in the course of the class hours. On the other hand, 28% indicate that they are sometimes carried out, and 10% indicate that they are rarely used. Values that are obtained because not all the activities carried out allow the students to express ideas, emotions or opinions. In this way, it is necessary to apply actions that develop and value the students' ideas and emotions.

7. Does the English teacher apply blank spaces within a text as activities to promote writing in the classroom?

Table 8 The teacher applies blank spaces

Alternatives	Frequency	Percentage
Always	4	10%
Frequently	22	55%
Sometimes	7	18%
Rarely	4	10%
Never	3	8%
Total	40	100%

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One of the activities mostly carried out by teachers is to fill in empty spaces in paragraphs with textual activities. For this reason, 55% indicate that these types of activities are frequently carried out. In the same way, 10% mention that there are always works in this way. These values indicate that it is necessary to continue with the development of the activities and encourage a more competitive development in the work, implementing strategies of vocabulary, grammar and punctuation.

8. During English class do you ask questions and open-ended answers in writing?

Table 9 Ask questions and open-ended answers

Alternatives	Frequency	Percentage
Always	1	3%
Frequently	1	3%
Sometimes	10	25%
Rarely	27	68%
Never	1	3%
Total	40	100%

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According to the results of the survey, according to whether during the English classes ask questions and open-ended answers in writing. 27 students representing 68% mention that this type of action is rarely carried out in the English class. On the other hand, 25% mention that these strategies are sometimes implemented. According to the students they mention that it is a complicated and complex aspect which they have not been able to fully understand.

9. Does the teacher uses assumptions about a topic as an activity to promote writing?

Table 10 The teacher use assumptions

Alternatives	Frequency	Percentage
Always	1	3%
Frequently	1	3%
Sometimes	4	10%
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According to the values dictated by the students, 75% mention that assumptions about a specific topic are rarely used for the purpose of promoting writing activities. In addition, 10% of students mention that such activities have never taken place. Values indicating that there are shortcomings in the teachers' methodology.

10. Does the teacher present formats that contain the process, steps or guidelines for the construction of written texts?

Table 11 The teacher presents formats that contain guidelines for written text

Alternatives	Frequency	Percentage
Always	1	3%
Frequently	1	3%
Sometimes	3	8%
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According to the results, 75% mention that the teacher has rarely shared formats that contain a process, steps or guidelines for the construction of paragraphs and small texts. Students need to know the correct use of grammar and sentences. However, at the time of developing a paragraph, or in the possible future an article or essay, it is necessary to know the steps that these include to make it in the best way and that it is understandable for the readers. In this way, it is considered necessary for teachers to encourage the development of the class with rules and procedures to follow for proper writing.

3.1. Participants

The participants selected for the study were first level students at CENID at Technical University of Babahoyo. In the same way, five educators of the subject of English were selected.

The students were between the ages of 17 and 19 years. The data collection process was done during class hours in the respective subject area of English. For the collection of data, it was necessary the authorization of the director and pass of the academic board, documents that have been properly annexed in this work of investigation. The research is feasible because there is full access to work with the participants of this study. In addition, each activity was carried out with the corresponding students assigned to the author. The collaboration of the authors' colleagues was essential to the development of this document.

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RESULTS

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Elaborated by: Beltrán Miguel, Cifuentes Thalia, García Paola and Menéndez Carlos, 2019

Figure 1 The teacher applies classroom projects

Elaborated by: Beltrán Miguel, Cifuentes Thalia, García Paola and Menéndez Carlos, 2019.

According to the results expressed by the students, sometimes the teacher carries out activities such as projects that allow the practice of writing skills, representing 60%, and 30% mention that these activities are frequently carried out. However, only 5% consider that these classroom strategies are used in a mandatory way in the classroom.

2. How often do you do essays or learning journals as an activity during English inter-language learning?

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3. Do the activities presented during the inter-learning process teach real or fictitious problems?

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4. Do the writing activities presented in English class allow students to express ideas, emotions, or opinions?

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Figure 4: Allow students to express ideas, emotions, or opinions

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According to the results expressed by the students, half of the class representing 50% mentions that frequently these activities are carried out in the course of the class hours. On the other hand, 28% indicate that they are sometimes carried out, and 10% indicate that they are rarely used. Values that are obtained because not all the activities carried out allow the students to express ideas, emotions or opinions. In this way, it is necessary to apply actions that develop and value the students' ideas and emotions.

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Figure 6 The teacher ask questions and open-ended answers

Elaborated by: Beltrán Miguel, Cifuentes Thalia, García Paola and Menéndez Carlos, 2019

According to the results of the survey, to whether during the English classes ask question ns and open-ended answers in writing. 27 students representing 68% mention that this type of action is rarely carried out in the English class. On the other hand, 25% mention that these strategies are sometimes implemented. According to the students they mention that it is a complicated and complex aspect which they have not been able to fully understand.

6. Does the teacher uses assumptions about a topic as an activity to promote writing?

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Figure 7 The teacher use assumptions

Elaborated by: Beltrán Miguel, Cifuentes Thalia, García Paola and Menéndez Carlos, 2019

According to the values dictated by the students, 75% mention that assumptions about a specific topic are rarely used for the purpose of promoting writing activities. In addition, 10% of students mention that such activities have never taken place.

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Never	5	13%
Total	40	100%

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Figure 8 The teacher presents formats that contain guidelines for written text

Elaborated by: Beltrán Miguel, Cifuentes Thalia, García Paola and Menéndez Carlos, 2019

According to the results, 75% mention that the teacher has rarely shared formats that contain a process, steps, rubrics or guidelines for the construction of paragraphs and small texts. Students need to know the correct use of grammar and sentences. However, at the time of developing a paragraph, or in the possible future an article or essay, it is necessary to know the steps that these include to make it in the best way and that it is understandable for the readers. In this way, it is considered necessary for teachers to encourage the development of the class with rules and procedures to follow for proper writing.

INTERVIEW ANALYSIS

Attitude towards writing in English

1. Do you like to make compositions in English?

The first question in the interview with teachers refers to teachers' attitudes towards writing. Among the results, a greater tendency to taste the composition of writing stands out. However, some disagreement with writing was noted according to the experts.

However, if teachers strongly support writing, the students' attitude towards the writing process should take a different path. The question supports this assumption, as it shows an obvious contrast between teacher feedback and student feedback. In this way, teachers insisted that they encourage students to read so that they would become better writers. On the other hand, teachers mention that in their class students do not read any text before they start writing. In this way, they recommend that students read the composition exercise, follow their instructions, and write a well-formed paragraph. In fact, teachers only mention the importance of reading, but they do not really encourage or motivate students to read.

2. What kind of writings do you like to do?

When considering the theme of composition, feedback from teachers coincides with that from students; not all teachers give students the opportunity to choose the theme. In fact, the analysis of the students' questionnaire connects this limitation with their negative approach to writing. In addition, the interview investigates the personal opinions of the teachers. In particular, teachers were asked whether the syllable has sufficient writing exercises. In this sense, the English teachers do not agree, as they believe in adding more writing exercises. However, all teachers agree that there is not enough time to teach all the exercises included in the book.

3. What do you feel when you are asked to make a composition in English?

According to the teachers' response, the limited amount of time devoted to writing may hamper teachers' ability to use technology. This being its disadvantage, since the use of methodological uses assisted by computer in tools such as Microsoft Office, facilitates the writing process, in addition to speeding up the time in the creation of compositions for students.

4. What is your greatest fear when communicating in written form in English?

Without a doubt, teachers know that the English language is part of the professional life of their students, as well as being a tool for mass communication. Therefore, teachers agreed that the greatest challenge and their greatest concern in matters of written communication is that students do not reach an adequate development and have difficulties in their professional life. Therefore, all teachers recommend students to have private tutoring or to join special courses in their free time apart from the one where written communication is focused. The limited time allocated to writing may have prompted teachers to adapt this point of view.

Aspects of grammatical competence

5. What do you think are the most mistakes you make when writing in English?

"Teachers should also strive to overcome students' writing difficulties," say some interviewees. According to estimates by fellow English teachers, students say they are not in favor of writing because of grammatical and spelling errors. In this sense, teachers recognize these obstacles by believing that such errors lead to poor writing. They also confirm that students have a low level of proficiency in other language skills, such as reading, speaking and listening.

DISCUSSION

According to the analysis of the student survey, students appear to have negative attitudes towards writing in English. Thus, great efforts must be made to motivate students about the role of writing in their lives. For example, students should appreciate the influence of writing on their psychological conditions. In fact, writing has the ability to release stress by overcoming its negative effects on the psychology of the individual.

The type of writing used to release stress is called "expressive writing" (). While the individual writes about certain harmful experiences, the student expresses what is hidden deep within his heart. In this way, instead of seeing writing as a source of stress, students will begin to write daily, small exercises. Therefore, the association between writing and healthy psychology will create positive effects on the students. As a result, a better tolerance for academic writing.

As a result, the starting point will be to motivate students to write in the target language, in this case English, without insisting on academic writing. As this partnership is strongly built, students will be ready to receive instructions regarding academic writing.

The role of the teacher, then, becomes fundamental. Teachers should elevate students' academic skills in all aspects of language. The writing process will be much easier if listening, reading and speaking skills are improved. Therefore, both students and teachers must increase efforts to develop students' language skills.

In addition, many students affirmed the fact that grammatical and orthographic errors leave negative influences on their attitudes towards writing. If the student continues to write without feeling sure of what he or she is writing, writing becomes an unbearable burden. It will also force them to feel bored, stressed, and unproductive because everything they write will be over-edited.

While practicing writing in English, students face several language difficulties. First, students' knowledge of grammatical and orthographic rules is limited. Certainly, many students make basic grammatical errors and continue to edit the spelling of their words as they write.

The lack of necessary vocabulary is another obstacle that hinders students' learning process. Once they write in class, students begin to ask the teacher about the meaning of the different words. In addition, the teacher notified the students that they use translation programs in an attempt to find meanings for the words.

In addition, students are unaware of writing assignments. For example, they are not familiar with tasks that facilitate the writing process, such as writing an outline. They also don't read any text before they start writing. Therefore, it is often difficult for students to develop ideas, or to cope with what is known as the writer's block.

Consequently, students find that writing is a tedious and stressful process that consumes effort, yet good grades can hardly be achieved. Therefore, most of them have already lost confidence in what they write.

Students, at this level, are supposed to receive knowledge and process it. As second language learners, they are not expected to work on their own to expand their writing skills. Most learners focus on improving their listening and reading skills. However, they are also responsible for their commitment to follow the teacher's instructions.

In this case, students should make every effort to actively participate in the class. Consequently, the teacher will be encouraged to further develop his teaching methods. The student will then have the opportunity to devote more time and develop in the English language.

On the other hand, teachers rarely practice writing in English. In fact, this assumption is demonstrated by teachers' assertion that writing is a time-consuming process. Gradually, teachers lose their high skills because they no longer practice. Therefore, many teachers recommend that students have private tutoring. They also find the long process of teaching difficult, or even impossible to carry out. Therefore, they neglect the need to practically motivate students to acquire professional standards.

It is also important for the teacher to take into account the different levels of students when teaching writing. Therefore, he needs to prepare exercises that are adapted to the multiple levels of the students. In addition, the composition of teaching involves the explanation of various tasks. It is not a lesson that students master immediately, but it is composed of multiple processes that need to be developed together. Teaching also includes fundamentals of grammar, punctuation, reading and listening comprehension. In addition, teachers must familiarize students with different writing styles.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusions

After applying, analyzing and processing the data collection instruments, concrete information could be obtained which could help the researcher to draw the following conclusions:

It was concluded that the students have deficiencies in writing skills and therefore obtain an intermediate level, due to the limited application of written activities in the English class. Therefore, teachers must use didactic tools to improve and strengthen the development of productive skills (Writing).

It was determined that students present difficulties in the application of the writing process, either due to lack of guidance in the process by the teacher, which affects the performance of students during writing activities at the time of organizing their ideas and identifying and thus correcting errors.

It was analyzed that using personal diaries as a didactic tool in the development of written activities in the teaching-learning process of the English language contribute positively in the production of the foreign language since the students have the opportunity to relate different writings of interest and motivation such as: stories, letters, compositions, messages, etc., in order to strengthen the writing process. It should be emphasized that writing helps us to think, to discover new ideas, to organize our critical thinking i.e. it is a key competence for our personal and intellectual development.

There is not enough knowledge of the various assessment techniques applied by teachers to help students develop their English writing skills. Hence the need to make a conscious study of writing techniques and scientifically substantiate them to use the most appropriate and help the student to write better.

Teachers are not trained in the application of various assessment techniques in the writing process, it is necessary to get used to the correct use of them to help better develop the students' written English skills. Teachers are unaware of the use of rubrics as a technique to evaluate the skill of the writing process. The alternative approach offered by this research can optimize the application of writing techniques and strengthen the level of writing in students.

Recommendations

It is proposed that teachers be made aware of and trained in the knowledge and management

of the different evaluation techniques so that they may help in the development of the process of writing the English language, on a permanent and systematic basis, with the aim of creating an evaluation culture in the institution. Teachers should make a commitment to teach the writing process and seek assessment techniques according to the knowledge and understanding of their students empowering them in terms of personal, professional and institutional growth.

Encourage the application of written activities in which students can practice the English language in order to achieve a good academic performance in the proper development of writing as well as promoting the performance of one of the language skills with higher priority in a foreign language.

Develop the writing process in the English class through each of its different stages: pre-writing, writing and post-writing, facilitate the student to organize their ideas and manifest them accurately for their proper development in order to acquire mastery of the written language and competence to express and develop critical thinking, teachers must be updated in the different assessment techniques, with permanent innovations as it is the best way to reach the learning of students in the writing process.

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